

IMP

BOX

DELIVERABLE REPORT

WP2 Dissemination, communication,
exploitation

D2.4

Communication Kit

WP Leader: **Promoscience**

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01/04/2021	

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5. Katholieke Universiteit Leuven (KU Leuven), Belgium, partner
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7. Karolinska Institutet (KI), Sweden, partner
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PROJECT SUMMARY

Despite the abundant and ubiquitous presence of micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs), knowledge on their prevalence and potentially harmful effects on human health are limited. The Imptox project aims to fill this gap by providing innovative solutions and approaches for evaluating MNP impact on the environment and food chain, their presence in animals and plants, and their effect on human allergy and asthma.

MNP surfaces may attract and retain hazardous contaminants such as metals, allergens, pathogenic bacteria and toxins, and deliver them into the body. Therefore, Imptox will focus on the effects of MNPs combined with contaminants to evaluate whether ingested and inhaled MNPs augments allergic disease. Imptox will develop novel tools to identify, extract, characterize, and quantify MNPs from food, the environment, and in exposed animals, focusing on assessing MNP prevalence based on size, shape and type. Labelled MNPs will be used to evaluate MNP fate, accumulation, toxicity in pre-clinical studies, and clinical research will investigate the relationship between MNP exposure and allergic disease in children.

Imptox scientific data will provide a basis for policy discussions at the national and European level on human health hazards and risks, food safety, use of plastic food packaging materials, MNP levels in drinking water and water used for crop irrigation, dietary advice for patients with allergic disease, respiratory health and others.

WORK PACKAGE 2 – MAIN AIMS & TASKS

The overall objective of WP 2 is to effectively **communicate** project ideas and activities carried out within the scope of the project to different target audiences, to **disseminate** results and to **transfer knowledge** to policymakers and stakeholders so they can act upon it.

More specifically, WP 2 aims to disseminate the project's outputs by addressing a large variety of actors potentially interested in Imptox's results as well as to exploit results by submitting recommendations to policy makers, thereby transferring evidence-based knowledge to decision makers for the purpose of better governance. Furthermore, various routes to assure scientific advancement will be routinely explored through the publication of e.g. SOPs, technical notes or through commercial exploitation.

In order to reach the objectives set in work-package two, various tasks have been defined:

- A communication and dissemination plan has been established defining target-oriented communication and dissemination actions. Further details can be found in deliverable D2.1.
- The following tools have been identified through which to communicate with the target audience:
 - o A strong project identity and logo described in deliverable D2.1.
 - o The project's website described in detail in deliverable D2.2.
 - o A **Communication Kit**, including a corporate presentation, leaflet, poster and a roll-up explained in detail further down.
 - o Social Media, explained in detail in deliverable D2.1.
- With the tools provided in this work-package, communication and dissemination activities are being implemented by establishing and pursuing relationships with the media through press releases, tailor-made press-kits, appealing infographics, etc. Furthermore, to help promote awareness about Imptox, social media channels have been activated. A dialogue with stakeholder groups will be.

established for the purpose of networking activities and partners will be encouraged to take part in scientific conferences as well as calls for articles in scientific journals. A final event will be held in the form of an international conference and networking event.

- The impact of communication activities will be traced and analysed through a monitoring tool.
- The project's results will be made available to stakeholders and policymakers in a reserved area of the webpage through a final online report summarising the outcomes. In close collaboration with the JRC, the project's outcomes will contribute to the definition of relevant guidance documents to regarding MNPs and health. Finally, in order to protect new analytical approaches, a patent search and market analysis will be carried out.

THE COMMUNICATION KIT

A tool to communicate effectively with different target audiences

The present deliverable describes the results achieved within Task 2.2. "Communication Tools". This task includes the development of a communication kit to facilitate the communication with different target audiences. The communication kit will support the work-package leader and all members of the consortium throughout the three main tasks of this work-package: communication, dissemination and exploitation.

The following materials have been produced so far:

- Leaflet
- Rollup
- Poster
- Corporate Presentation

Further materials are envisaged at a later stage of the project duration, including videos, interviews, educational games, webinars and interactive tools to communicate research results.

The messages transmitted in the various materials at different levels of detail are the following:

- Micro- and nanoplastics pollution is ubiquitous, as MNPs can be found anywhere in our ecosystem, even inside the human body.
- Science currently doesn't have the tools to understand the problem in depth.
- Imptox will help address that problem by developing new analytical tools to understand what impact MNPs may have on human health, while focusing in particular on the relationship between MNPs and allergic disease.
- Potentially harmful environmental contaminants adhering to MNP surfaces can end up in the human body through ingestion or inhalation. In Imptox scientists will try to understand the impact of MNPs together with the cargo they carry.
- Imptox is a multidisciplinary consortium of 12 partners from 8 European countries
- Imptox is financed by the European Horizon 2020 Framework Programme and collaborates with other four projects (AURORA, Polyrisk, Plasticheal and PlasticsFatE) forming CUSP, the European

research cluster to understand the health impacts of micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs).

- Imptox collaborates with Non-Governmental Organizations, stakeholders from industry, business, scientists and policymakers to provide decision makers, risk assessors and regulators with data to safeguard the environment and human health.

All communication materials are in line with the project’s visual identity and logo design as explained in great detail in deliverable D2.1. Furthermore, all materials make reference to the EU funds and prompt the reader to act upon the material by inviting them to visit the Imptox website, follow its social media and connect with via secretariat@imptox.eu

The current communication materials are explained in detail in the next section.

Leaflet

The Imptox leaflet consists of a 10-page long brochure describing in further detail the project’s objectives, its workplan, the consortium, CUSP and how to get in touch with Imptox. The booklet is designed for printing in the format 12 x 12 centimetres, with a cover page of 20 x 12 centres. It is browsable and optimized for PC reading and easy desktop printing. Further down a mock-up of the brochure and some internal pages for the purpose of demonstration.

THE PROBLEM

Micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) are tiny plastic particles that form when larger items of plastic degrade, or are manufactured and added to commercial products, such as synthetic textiles, cosmetics or paints. These minuscule pieces can be found anywhere on earth including our bodies as they enter our organism through food, water and air; yet we currently neither have the tools to characterise and quantify them, nor do we understand how they affect human health.

IMP TOX

A scientific project to understand the health effects of **micro- and nanoplastics pollution**, with a focus on allergic disease

THE PROJECT

"In Imptox we intend to untangle the multifaceted relationship of exposure routes, risks and health impacts of MNPs, while focusing in particular on allergic disease"

Tanja Ćirković Veličković
Imptox Coordinator, University of Belgrade

STUDYING THE RELATIONSHIP WITH ALLERGIC DISEASES

To understand if MNPs in food and air can promote or worsen peoples' allergies.

IMPROVING MNP DETECTION

By developing innovative tools to detect, measure, characterize and track MNPs in food, water and air.

INVESTIGATING MNPS COMBINED WITH POLLUTANTS

To evaluate the impact of MNPs as vectors for potentially toxic materials adsorbed to their surface, including metals, toxins, allergens, pathogenic bacteria.

We are a multidisciplinary team of scientists with expertise in a wide range of fields including food sciences, allergy, immunology, biomedicine, chemistry, bioinformatics and others.

OUTREACH & GUIDANCE

We plan to deliver data and its ramifications to help decision makers, risk assessors and regulators safeguard our air, water and food supply. For that purpose we plan to work closely with Non-Governmental Organizations, stakeholders from industry, business, scientists and policymakers.

SYNERGIES IN ACTION

Imptox is one of five Horizon 2020 projects that form **The European Research Cluster to Understand the Health Impacts of Micro- and Nanoplastics, CUSP**. The CUSP team will work closely with the European Commission's Joint Research Centre to enhance the impact of their research and to ensure constant dialogue between science and policymaking.

Poster

An A1 poster has been developed to promote Imptox at partner institutions and their research facilities as well as conferences, talks and events. The poster gives the reader a quick overview of the project, presenting its main aims and the Imptox consortium.

A scientific project to understand the health effects of micro- and nanoplastics with a focus on allergic disease

Micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) are tiny plastic particles that form when larger items of plastic degrade, or are manufactured and added to commercial products. These minuscule pieces can be found anywhere on earth including our bodies, as they enter our organism through food, water and air, yet **we currently do not understand how they affect human health.**

THE PROJECT

Untangling the multifaceted relationship of exposure routes, risks and health impacts of MNPs

IMPROVING MNP DETECTION

By developing innovative tools to detect, measure, characterize and track MNPs in a variety of foods, water and air.

INVESTIGATING MNPs COMBINED WITH POLLUTANTS

To evaluate the impact of MNPs as vectors for potentially toxic materials adsorbed to their surface, including metals, toxins, allergens, pathogenic bacteria.

STUDYING THE RELATIONSHIP WITH ALLERGIC DISEASES

To examine the possible link between MNPs and their role in promoting food allergy and allergic asthma.

THE IMPTOX TEAM

A multidisciplinary consortium of 12 partners from 8 European countries.

- BELGIUM
UGENT
- AUSTRIA
KI
- MOVERIM
- AUSTRIA
MUW
- KULeuven
- CROATIA
UniVien
- Sicensano
- SCH
- SWITZERLAND
HES-SO
- SERBIA
UNIVERSITET
- FRANCE
CNRS
- HFUB
- ITALY
Promoscience

Imptox has received funding from the EU's H2020 framework programme for research and innovation under grant agreement n. 965173. This project is part of CUSP, the European research cluster to understand the health impacts of micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs).

Contact us at
www.imptox.eu
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follow us

Roll-up

The project roll-up has been developed for display at partner institutions, events, conferences, talks, etc. Like the poster, it summarises the project in a nutshell, while the title gives the reader an immediate clue as to what the project is about.

Corporate Presentation

The Imptox corporate presentation has been prepared with the aim to communicate the project and its main goals clearly and effectively to different audiences. For this purpose, it contains slides with varying degrees of detail, depending on the audience the presenter is addressing. The presentation is roughly structured according to:

- Imptox Main Objectives
- The Consortium
- Workplan
- Work-Packages
 - General Slide
 - Scientific Slide(s)
- Imptox is part of CUSP

Here a mock-up of the corporate presentation and some of its internal slides.

These materials will be downloadable from the project’s intranet side, accessible through the Imptox website. They are intended to help Imptox gain visibility among the general public, researchers and stakeholders by providing information about the project and its outputs on printed material for static display or online. For this purpose, Promoscience has also designed different banners to be used in social media communications and to gain visibility in the web.

